

REVIEW OF GLOBAL PRODUCTION AND MARKET ANALYSIS OF BIOPLASTIC PACKAGING

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Abstract: *Packaging generates environmental impact throughout its life cycle, so developing new packaging solutions is necessary to minimize environmental pollution. The rising environmental concerns owing to the increasing amount of plastic packaging waste across the globe, especially across developing economies, are driving the demand for bioplastic packaging. The bioplastic packaging market is predicted to increase significantly as a result of the strict regulatory environment, the worldwide environmental crisis, and other factors. Accordingly, the present review study deals with market size analysis, market share, growth factors as well as future forecasts in bioplastics packaging.*

Keywords: bioplastics, packaging, sustainability, environment, market analysis, CAGR

1 INTRODUCTION

Packaging development has become a great challenging task and of enormous responsibility for the manufacturers and the professionals involved (Bucci et al., 2007). Businesses are under pressure not only from consumers but also from governments to use eco-friendly packaging for their products (Nguyen et al., 2020).

More than 70% of the world's largest companies have committed themselves to reducing plastics pollution. It was recently concluded that the implementation of “circular innovations” for packaging on a global level is still low (Lisiecki et al., 2023). As a result of plastic waste, Earth’s ocean and freshwater biodiversity and ecosystems are being negatively affected. The magnitude of plastic pollution carried to sea has significantly multiplied over the past several decades. Oftentimes, wildlife is injured due to entanglement or ingestion of the plastics

found in the environment. For Procellariiformes such as the albatrosses, shearwaters, or petrels, the appearance of eroded plastic pieces are similar to many types of food they consume. Microplastics resemble phytoplankton which are eaten by fish and cetaceans. Ingested plastic debris has been found to reduce stomach capacity, hinder growth, cause internal injuries, and create intestinal blockage. Plastic entanglement with fishing nets or other ring-shaped materials can result in strangulation, reduction of feeding efficiency, and in some cases drowning (Sigler, 2014).

Growing concern about human health and environmental aspects has driven the focus more towards eco-friendly, biodegradable, and sustainable packaging materials (Surendren et al., 2022). In that sense, seeking new sustainable materials to replace petroleum-based plastics has led to the development of a new group of materials, termed bioplastics. The term bioplastic is mostly used to define plastics that can be either bio-based, biodegradable, or both (Shlush et al., 2022). Bioplastics are not just one single material. They comprise of whole family of materials with different properties and applications. The term ‘biobased’ means that the material or product is (partly) derived from biomass (plants). Biomass used for bioplastics stems from e.g. corn, sugarcane, or cellulose.

Figure 1. Material coordinate system for bioplastics (Bioplastics, 2023).

With respect to environmental impact, as opposed to their fossil- and petrol-based counterparts, polymers from natural sources significantly reduce the final product carbon footprint, the industry dependency on scarce resources and

leads to lower emission of greenhouse gas and other toxic compounds to the atmosphere (Shlush et al., 2022).

Bioplastics are gaining significant traction and they are suitable for a broad range of end-of-life options, including packaging. The expanding trend of sustainability in many packaging elements is driving the bioplastic packaging market. Due to the widespread use of packaging products and the rising aversion to plastic packaging with a high risk of contamination, the food and beverage sectors are recognized as the top consumers of bioplastic packaging. (Bioplastics Packaging Market, 2023).

This is owing to high consumer awareness, supportive government initiatives, and continuous innovation in biodegradable packaging in the market. Stringent regulations over conventional plastic use in food, beverage, and medical packaging has led to increasing adoption of these (Bioplastics Packaging Market, 2022).

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

Market analysis is a comprehensive study of a specific market within an industry, including an examination of its various components, such as market size and trends, target audience, profitability and growth rate (Market Analysis, 2023). The aim of this review paper was to evaluate and understand bioplastic packaging market. The analysis is based on open-access market reports from 2022 to 2030.

2.1 Global production of bioplastics

Currently, bioplastics still represent < 1% of the more than 390 million tonnes of plastic produced annually. After stagnating in 2020, mainly due to Covid-19, the overall global plastic production has been increasing again since 2021. This development is driven by rising demand combined with the emergence of more sophisticated applications and products.

According to the latest market data, the global bioplastics production capacities are set to increase from around 2.2 million tonnes in 2022 to approximately 6.3 million tonnes in 2027. Figure 2 shows the global production capacities of bioplastics in tones in period 2021-2027.

Figure 2. Global production capacities of bioplastics, 2022-2027.

Bioplastics are used in an increasing number of markets, from packaging, catering products, consumer electronics, automotive, agriculture/horticulture, and toys to textiles and several other segments. Packaging remains the largest market segment for bioplastics with 48% (almost 1.1 million tonnes) of the total bioplastics market in 2022. However, the portfolio of applications continues to diversify. Segments, such as automotives & transport or building & construction, remain on the rise with growing capacities of functional polymers.

Figure 3. Global production capacities of bioplastics 2022 (by market segment).

With a view to regional capacity development, Asia further strengthened its position as major production hub with more than 41% of bioplastics currently being produced in the region. Presently, just over a quarter of the production capacity is still located in Europe. However, Europe's share and that of other

world regions will significantly decrease within the next five years. In contrast, Asia's production capacities are predicted to increase to almost 63% by 2027.

Figure 4. Global production capacities of bioplastics 2027 (by region) (Bioplastics, 2023, Ferreira et al., 2023).

2. 2 Market size and growth rate

Market size refers to the total sales generated in a specific period and provides insight into the current sales volume and future sales projections. Market size is influenced by market demand, and businesses can gather information on market size through surveys, government data, trade publications, and financial reports (Market Analysis, 2023).

The changed post Covid-19 business landscape, the global market for plastic packaging estimated at USD 702.4 Billion in the year 2022, is projected to reach a revised size of USD 944.3 Billion by 2030, growing at a CAGR (Compound Annual Growth Rate) of 3.8% over the analysis period 2022-2030.

Figure 5. Global market for plastic packaging.

However, the increasing need for sustainable materials has developed a dynamic rise in bioplastics production in the upcoming years. The global bioplastic packaging market size was exhibited at USD 15.6 Billion in 2022 and is projected to attain around USD 58 Billion by 2032, growing at a CAGR of 14.02% during the forecast period 2023 to 2032.

Figure 6. Global market for bioplastic packaging.

2.3 Market share

The expanding trend of sustainability in many packaging elements is driving the bioplastic packaging market. Due to the widespread use of packaging products and the rising aversion to plastic packaging with a high risk of contamination, the food and beverage sectors are recognized as the top consumers of bioplastic packaging.

Regarding application, the food and beverage sector held a significant market share in 2022, accounting for 59% (Figure 7). The market is being driven by the increased prominence of quick-service restaurants and the demand for packaged food. The industry for flexible packaging will likely rise during the forecast period because manufacturers are expanding their production capacity in response to the rising demand for packaged goods.

Figure 7. Bioplastic packaging market share, by application in 2022.

In terms of revenue, the bioplastics packaging market in Europe held the highest share 34% in 2022. Due to strict environmental legislation and rising consumer concern for the environment, the region will likely experience significant growth in the years to come.

Figure 8. Bioplastic packaging market share, by region, 2022 (%).

Europe follows North America and the Asia Pacific region in terms of projected market expansion. The bioplastics packaging material market will likely grow significantly in Japan, the U.S., China, and Germany.

Government initiatives will also increase bioplastic demand over the evaluation period, such as the decision of the E.U. to lessen the widespread use of single-use plastic products. The European Parliament decided to ban single-use plastic products like cutlery and straws in 2019 as part of a comprehensive rule against plastic rubbish that damages beaches and pollutes waterways. In July 2021, a ban on single-use plastics was anticipated to go into effect (Bioplastics Packaging Market, 2023).

3 CONCLUSIONS

It is understood that one of the major benefits of going bioplastics packaging is the preservation and well-being of the environment we live in. Awareness and concerns about environmental issues are growing among consumers. Recent studies demonstrate that despite the economic crisis, consumers in developed countries affirm their wish for eco-friendly packaging more than ever before. Bioplastics are expected to displace conventional plastic in many industries due to the numerous benefits, especially in food and beverage packaging industry.

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Abbreviations: *PE - Polyethylene; PEF – Polyethylene Furanoate; PET - Polyethylene terephthalate; PTT - poly trimethylene terephthalate; PLA - Poly Lactic Acid; PHA – Polyhydroxyalkanoate; PBS - Polybutylene succinate; PP - Polypropylene; PMMA - Polymethylmethacrylate Acrylic; PVC - Polyvinyl chloride; PBAT - Polybutylene adipate terephthalate; PCL – Polycaprolactone.*

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